

EXPRESSION OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL SPIRIT IN CREATING AN AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL STORY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE STORY OF ISAJAN SULTAN "FRIEND")

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ABSTRACT: In this article, Isajon Sultan's method of creating autobiographical stories and the creation of his friend-story in a philosophical spirit and the content of the parts created based on the stages of the story are discussed. In the philosophical story, the story expressed as a result of the author's life period being divided into several stages and the addition of literary and artistic details is analyzed. Also, dates, characters have no place in the story, but the work is quite complex in terms of artistic value.

KEY WORDS: Autobiographical work, philosophical spirit, author's language, landscape image, folk language, motive.

Literature is a phenomenon that comes into direct contact with the life of society with various fields and events. That's why the role of autobiographical works in the analysis of literary works is different. When creating autobiographical stories, the attitude of the writer to his own life is expressed in a different way from the point of view of the society and the individual. In the literature of the world, there are concepts about the creation of autobiographical stories in a philosophical spirit, that is, it is important to outline the expression of one's life in full or according to certain changes. This can be seen in the life and work of Isajon Sultan. "If I asked you, you would shrug. You didn't even know what a dream was. You did not know about those areas and places that I saw.

What about me? Could I go back as soon as I found out about those places? The interesting thing is that what I saw in those places I was never hungry, thirsty, or sleepy, I was always tired... but when my soul came back to my body, I realized that what I saw was not real, it was something like a fantasy that surrounds my consciousness like a fog, sometimes I was happy, sometimes I was sad.

And you, so-and-so... quick and cute, cheerful and loyal boy with sparkling eyes... you were always by my side.

Eh-heh, what roads did we go through together with you... Do you remember when we picked cotton in the autumn fields, under the rain? Your hands are bruised and red, the boots on your thin legs are wet, you shivered, and then we lit a bonfire? It's strange that you didn't care if I was cold or hot, but you were always cold. What about the frost in the fields covered with beetles? Do you remember those of us who labored in the pouring snow, spring rains and summer heat? Yes, those labors seemed to be too much for you and me. We used to chop firewood, spread the snow on the snow, we would collect it and bring it home and light the fire, we would carry water from the stream that was blackened in the snow... your hands would get cold and red again, when we would go inside, you would shiver and lay down next to the stove. you could take it, friend. Then all I remember is that your nails have grown again.

Also, I remember your fingers disproportionate to your thin height and your big palm with a package.

Your joys are also simple, soulful, small things. I remember how happy you were when we picked and ate sweet pomegranates. Why don't you indulge in small pleasures?" [1]

In this story, expressed through memories, he relates what he saw in society as an elderly person. In the first places, friends compare and compare the past days with the purpose of remembering the person with whom they were together in good and bad times. He transfers all of his days spent with him, that is, his work in society, his difficulties, and his married life, to the image of a landscape. Accordingly, there are several stages in this autobiographical story. They are as follows:

1st stage. Image of childhood;

2nd stage. Memories of school years;

3rd stage. Puberty years;

4th stage. Old age.

In autobiographical novels, short stories, and stories, the realities are often more philosophical than relational. This is given directly by the writer based on certain signs and symbols without being openly revealed. The image of the landscape in the society is widely illuminated in the expression of the conflicting attitude. For example: "years have passed, we both grew up", a conversation between the author and a friend and himself is realized when the image style is implemented. Also, the story of Isajon Sultan's "friend" applies to all his friends who lived with him in the society. Since the creation of this story goes back to the first year, Isajon Sultan is in some sense a work created as a result of reminiscing about the years of his youth as an old man. According to some views on this, stories of this type are written as a dedication to a certain person, and in history, it was a tradition to create some expressions and verses in dedications to deceased loved ones in the forms of creation of literary and artistic works. The "friend" story may have originated from the fact that Isajon Sultan wrote a letter or a story in the form of a letter to a close friend, originating from the modern literary and artistic style. In the story "Dost" the name of a friend is not mentioned, but their childhood experiences, school days and life's hard trials together are embodied in the main plan.

The main emphasis is on the many memories of youth in old age and the formation of this story with regrets and thanks. The occurrence of this issue is also Isajon Su Unlike the philosophical works of Iton, it is related to friends. Expressing friendship with loyalty, the events in rural conditions, that is, the fact that two friends have never parted, are the events that caused the first to sacrifice his life for the second. Their lives are split into two as a result of the passing of their young years, and as a result of serving the tasks they want or don't want. It is a natural reality that the life of a friend in his old age is sick, he remembers his friend more and more as a result of difficulties in his life, and after his death, he feels lonely and friendless. In Isajon Sultani's stories " Longing ", " friend ", " Fate", we observe poetic changes in the genre of the story, which took place in the composition of the literary process of the independence period. In the story "Longing" he describes the changes in the human psyche in connection with the image of nature. In the above-mentioned stories of the writer, polyphonic image features are also embodied. There is a special meaning in the blowing of the wind in his stories. There is a certain meaning in the image of musica in the story, and we can see the contradictions in the path of human innocence. And in the story "Oydin Bulak", the

innocence of childhood memories, feelings about the beauty of young life, deeply imprinted on the human heart, make sure that they will never leave a person".[2]

Expressing the fact that his friend is suffering from his memories in an artistic image also reveals philosophy. It is not typical for every creator to simply increase the artistic value of a story by creating a story without giving certain dates, names, and characters. It can be said that Isajon Sultan's skill in using words, sincerity, and expression features that are close to the reader, caused this work to cause a great philosophical sensation. "The ending of the story attracts the reader's attention. It is a very difficult task to preserve the value of art without the participation of characters and heroes in the work. The philosophy of Isajon Sultan's work increased the value of the "friend" story. They are as follows:

- childish expression of pictorial expression;
- presentation of the author's language in a popular spirit;
- division of the story into certain sections;
- expression of sample motives in the story;
- the emotional power of the text and the fact that it is created in a simple language".[3]

At the end of the story, Isajon Sultan turns to his friend and concludes the sentences by saying, "You are still my friend, my friend." The person who read the same story sang about a person who had a conflict with a person after years of friendship, and as a result, he sang it in order to apologize to him or when he created expressions with a comforting meaning. It is the beginning of the Sultan's friend's story, "We were playing in the meadows, we were friends, we were friends", and it leads from the intense years of childhood to the end of the harsh years of the king's old age.

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